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Snow and the Veil: A Critical Study of the Symbolism of Snow in Richard Wright's *Haiku*

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Abstract:

Richard Wright was one of the most influential African American writers to achieve significant recognition in the history of African American literature. Among the less-explored literary works of Wright, *Haiku: The Last Poetry of Richard Wright*, which comprises almost 800 haiku written by him, bears testimony to how deeply Wright was affected by the unpleasant experiences he underwent as a person of African ancestry. This research article aims to decipher Wright's frequent use of snow imagery which appears to be a manifestation of his perception of racism and the way he adroitly used snow to symbolise the color line, and the veil, two ideas propounded by respectively by Frederick Douglass and W.E.B. Du Bois, along with the pain of isolation, alienation and loneliness.

Keywords: Snow, color line, the veil, racism.

Richard Wright was one of the recognised African American writers who attained immense popularity during the 1940s. However, his novels, such as *Uncle Tom's Children* (1938) and *Native Son* (1941) spurred controversy for the inclusion of sexuality, graphic description of atrocities and harsh depiction of reality; his lesser-known literary works, such as *Haiku: The Last Poetry of Richard Wright*, composed by him during his final years, demonstrated more nuanced artistic expression. It does not seem invidious to mention that Wright sought refuge in communist ideology to alleviate the pain inflicted by racism. Along with his communist ideas, his literary works also explored other aspects of society, such as his experiences in a racist world. Among his lesser-known works, *Haiku: The Last Poetry of Richard Wright* (1998) is the culmination of the profound knowledge he accumulated throughout his life and the perspective he developed during his final days of self-imposed exile in France. Whereas Wright's other notable poems, which speak volumes of racial injustice and disparities, such as *Between the World and Me* and *I Have Seen Black Hands*, the quintessential indictment of racial injustice, the haiku meditates on the aspects of an idyllic life with frequent inklings of racial dynamics, social isolation and alienation enveloped in the tenets of Zen philosophy. Interestingly, the poetic form Wright adapted to convey his feelings is an ancient Japanese form that flourished on the precepts of ancient Zen philosophy. The poet of haiku assumes a contemplative state (mu, or state of nothingness), often implemented by the practitioner of Zen philosophy, to meditate upon a particular scene. It is a short poem composed by the poet to express a single emotion generated from witnessing a specific phenomenon of nature. In *A Glossary of Literary Terms*, M.H. Abrams defines haiku in the following words: "Haiku is a Japanese poetic form that is represented in fourteen syllables, ordered into three lines of five, seven and five syllables." (Abrams 114) It registers the poet's response to a natural object, scene or season of the year. It is short and compact. Brevity and distinctiveness are the salient features of a haiku. These poems express a single idea, image or feeling concisely. Japanese

poets popularised it during the 16th century. Ezra Pound utilised the principles of haiku in his poems. Other notable poets, such as Amy Lowell, Robert Frost, and W. B. Yeats, were profoundly influenced by haiku and became eminent exponents of the genre. (Cuddon, 372)

When Richard Wright started experimenting with haiku writing, he was suffering intensely due to amoebic dysentery, which led to severe weight loss and physical exhaustion. He mentioned in a letter to his friend, “During my illness, I experimented with the Japanese form of poetry called haiku.” (Fabre 510) Wright comments, “These poems are the results of being in bed a great deal, and it is likely that they are bad. I don’t know.” (Fabre 511) The enervated state of Wright resulting from his disease, coupled with the psychological affliction caused by lifelong endurance of racial injustice, found expression in his haiku in the guise of snow. The imagery of snow employed by Wright can be interpreted as an emblem of hardship, racial segregation and the hurdles the coloured people encounter due to racial discrimination. In his haiku, snow envisages the white background as representative of the white American society. In contrast, the contrast displayed by juxtaposing snow and other black objects contributes to the formation of a metaphorical barrier manifested as the color line mentioned by Frederick Douglass or the veil defined by W.E.B. Du Bois.

Frederick Douglass was probably the first African American writer to identify the problem of American society. He writes, “The problem of the twentieth century is the problem of the color line”. Frederick Douglass, in his work *The Color Line*, published in *The North American Review*, vol. 132, in 1881, mentioned that the practice of “color prejudice” was not only prevalent in American society, but he also senses a propensity on the part of the white community to rationalise this color prejudice, which leads to the formation of the ‘color line’. He writes— “Out of this depth of slavery has come this prejudice and this color line. It is broad enough and black enough to explain all the malign influences which assail the newly emancipated millions today.”(p.573) He further expatiates – “Every man who had a thousand

reasons for painting the black man as fit only for slavery, having made him the companion of horses and mules, he naturally sought to justify himself by assuming that the negro was not much better than a mule.” The Color Line, as F. Douglass opines, works subconsciously and thwarts black people’s growth to their full potential.

A radically similar conviction was developed in the compelling work, *The Souls of the Black Folk*, by W.E.B. Du Bois, who postulated about an invisible ‘veil’ existing in the society that demarcates the black and white lives. He used the term ‘the veil’ to describe the way racism made it difficult for whites to identify blacks as true Americans. Therefore, the blacks also accepted the identity portrayed by the whites. The veil resides between two worlds, the black and the white. He assumed that the veil created a separate identity that blacks experienced as they felt both African and American at the same time. The veil can be deciphered in three ways. It indicates the literal darker skin of the black people, secondly, the white people’s inability to see black people as true Americans. Lastly, Black people’s lack of a clear notion about themselves refutes the prevailing white-centric perception.

In order to amplify the concept of the veil and its manifestation in diverse forms, DuBois coined another term, “double consciousness”. DuBois explained double consciousness as: “Each of us helplessly and forever contains the other _ - male in female, female in male, white in black, black in white.” According to him- “The worst feature of this double consciousness is that the two lives, of the understanding and the soul, white lead, really show minimal relation to each other.” DuBois offered an excellent definition for this social scenario _ - “Two souls, two thoughts, two unreconciled strivings; two warring ideals in one dark body, whose dogged strength alone keeps it from being torn asunder.” He writes- “one ever feels his two – ness- an American, a Negro.”

“The double life of every American Negro must live, as a Negro and as an American, leads inevitably to a “painful self-consciousness, an almost morbid sense of personality and a moral hesitancy which is fatal to the self-confidence.” The resultant “double life with double thoughts, double duties and double social classes, double words and double ideas” according to Du Bois, scar the mind of a person of mixed race. Double consciousness, as Du Bois explained in his *The Souls of the Black Folk* in 1903, is the effect that racism had on black identity or the way Black American people construed their identity under the scrutiny of the white gaze. It is an internal conflict experienced by a subordinate or colonised group in an oppressive society. DuBois identified double consciousness as a psychological challenge, a feeling of always looking at oneself through the eyes of a white racist society. He expatriates the way Black American people interpreted the meaning of being black. The entire process of developing a double consciousness occurs subconsciously. The white society, which has prevented African Americans from achieving a free social status and equality even after the abolition of slavery, will continue to create obstacles in their path. Carl Gustav Jung also wrote about the predicament of an African American, that the most shocking thing about it was that black culture was not equal, but also not separate. He wrote, “The naive European thinks of America as a white nation. It is not wholly white if you please, it is partly coloured.” The slightly negroid mannerisms of the American can be explained by that theory. He further continues, “Since the Negro lives within your cities and even within your houses, he also lives within your skin subconsciously.”. In his *Prospero and Caliban: The Psychology of Colonization*, Octave Mannoni observes that the inferiority of coloured people springs from physical differences, especially skin colour. It occurs when certain psychological and sociological conditions are unfulfilled. Similarly, an African American’s concept of their identity is very much imbued with the white people’s manner of perceiving someone black, which further problematises the Black perspective on American society.

In order to decipher the symbolism of snow in Wright's haikus, the idea of double consciousness, the concept of the veil and the color line should be implemented in this context. The pure white colour of the snow is often contrasted against a dark object or background in order to accentuate the difference and draw a segregating line. This demarcation represents the veil that exists as an eternal, insurmountable barrier between the white and black worlds. Snow represents the superior one, the cherished object, and even a respectable one. While often juxtaposed against a dark background, the snow's whiteness is highlighted. The snow inspires respect, along with enhancing the scene's beauty. (35) Wright uses snow as the symbol of the white world, often inadvertently announcing its superiority when pitted against the black backdrop. Frantz Fanon illustrated this black and white binary in his ground-breaking work *Black Skin, White Masks*. He talked about the "white gaze" which expected him to behave like a black man, a nigger. Fanon's concern regarding his self-image intensifies as he "had to meet the white man's eyes" a situation that weighs him down with unfamiliar weight. Therefore, this cumbersome existence of Fanon resulted from an incredible amount of pressure, as "In the white world, the man of colour encounters difficulties in the development of his bodily schema. Fanon further writes about his struggle to be designated as a man, a status which is attained only by being born as one, but often denied to African Americans due to the colour of their skin."

"I discovered my blackness, my ethnic characteristics, and I was battered down by tom-toms, cannibalism, intellectual deficiency, fetishism, racial defects, slave ships" (p.112). In almost every culture, the colour white symbolises purity; on the contrary, black colour indicates evil." The Negro is an animal, the Negro is bad, the Negro is mean, the Negro is ugly; look, a nigger."

The stereotypical images projected by the racially biased society from their Eurocentric perspective are evident in the popular literature produced by them. The inferiority complex, according to Fanon, is instilled in the minds of the black little boys from their very childhood

when they unconsciously imbibe the concept of bad negro while consuming children magazines. Fanon vindicated the fact in the following passage-“In the magazines the Wolf, the Devil, the Evil spirit, the Bad Man, the Savage are always symbolised by Negroes or Indians; since there is always identification with the victory, the little Negro, quite as easily as the little white boy becomes an explorer, an adventurer, a missionary” who faces the danger of being eaten by the wicked Negroes.”(p.146)

The loneliness and melancholy note that emanates in Wright’s haiku is representative of the accrued pain engendered from receiving discriminatory behaviour from society. Wright identified that one of the primary causes of global racial injustice was the imaginative poverty of the white listeners. In his collection of lectures, *White Man Listen*, he evinced that white people were incapable of perceiving black people as ‘full human beings’, a discrepancy which Wright referred to as “a singular poverty of imagination.” Instead, the white people, due to their imaginative insolvency, perceive the black people as human with certain discrepancies. His haikus express the pain of isolation and loneliness resulting from Wright’s deliberation on the issue of racial segregation. Wright shared his observation regarding the coldness in white people’s behaviour towards his community and wrote- “Do not, with the false kindness of the missionaries and businessmen, drag out this agony for another five hundred years while your villages rot and your people’s minds sink into the morass of subjective darkness....Be merciful by being stern! If I lived under your regime, I’d ask for this hardness, this coldness.” (*Black Power*, P.103) Simultaneously, the double consciousness and identity crises are issues that have been implicitly or sometimes explicitly expressed in Wright’s haiku. In haiku 31, a black boy is trying to catch snow only to make his hand white. In the haiku, the black boy covers his palms with snow until they are white. The imagery is pregnant with racist references as the incident indicates physical transformation induced by external forces (such as society, as the white gaze propelled the black people towards whitening), so impactful that it can alter an

individual's identity. Aime Cesaire wrote about the process of thingification in *Discourse on Colonialism*. In his influential essay *Discourse on Colonialism*, Aimé Césaire refers to the process of thingification, which renders colonised subjects as objects or things to be exploited and transforms them into instruments for the economic and political advantage of the colonisers. He contends that colonialism dehumanises both the colonised and the coloniser. Thingification manifests in diverse forms like forced labour, economic exploitation, violence and intimidation, and cultural erasure. This proclivity erases the hereditary and cultural aspects of a person hailing from a black family, which is ostensible in the attempt at whitening on the part of the poet. Fanon also discussed this 'imaginary whitening' in his *Black Skin, White Masks*, which, according to him, results in profound psychological alienation and fragmented self-image. Similarly, in haiku 33, the boy's attempt to write his name on the snow-covered porch is emblematic of his desperation to formulate an identity. In haiku 61, he describes a scene where a brown horse's back turns white when covered by snow. This obsession with snow and the ability to transform every darker object into a white one reflects psychological conditioning, often referred to as "imaginary whitening." When Wright portrayed a scene where snow covered the dark object, transforming it into a white one, he inadvertently activated the process of thingification mentioned by Aimé Césaire. The image of snow has been replicated in haiku no. 161,164,166,185,212,280,325,335,341, 410,611,613,616, and 752. Other haiku, like 373,377,414,702,703,746, directly placed snow on a black object to highlight the contrast between black and white. Phrases like, black umbrella in the falling snow, winter dusk black cow, frozen black timbers, snow melting, dark hedges patches of white, black poles and sticky snow, snow against the black water, black rat in the snow, (790) black cock in the snow (523) became a recurrent pattern in his haiku. Moreover, the use of phrases like gleaming snow, the shadow of the horse that bites into the snow, the black man sweeping steel in falling snow, black winter hill and lighted window drastically intensifies the contrast of black and

white. The black people and shadows appear repeatedly in haiku, like 609,455,530,452, and images of dark and long shadows in 89,95,99,102,103, 419. Wright's obsession with the colour white is evident in the recurring image of the magnolia, the whitewashed wall, and the whiteness of the snow. However, he made the contrast of black and white conspicuous by the subtle juxtaposition of objects, such as dark, long shadows, dark objects, and fresh white magnolias, as well as white-washed walls and ice-covered landscapes. The snow imagery has recurred in Wright's haiku only to underscore the agony of alienation and social isolation. The coldness and starkness of winter symbolise feelings of loneliness and isolation, accompanied by the hardship, challenges and obstacles faced by black people in a racially biased world. His ability is unparalleled when it comes to using snow imagery to achieve the desired effect and convey his message simultaneously. Snow in Richard Wright's haiku explicitly symbolises beauty, a revered aspect of nature. Whereas, on a covert level, it is emblematic of the white-coloured skin, an object long admired and coveted by the black man. It has been exemplified in these lines -

The children walk timidly/respecting the snow (35)

He often admires the beauty of an "ice coated window" (280) or ice-wagon and snow-white pigeon (335) or "long drifts of snow on a mountain ridge." (185) In other haiku, light flakes of snow (710), snow fall (341,410,611,616) seem to enhance the beauty of nature. Snow is also associated with visual and auditory comfort and relaxation. (161,164)

A solid cake of snow/sliding off a roof (161)

In haiku 164, the poet wonders about the reason behind his sound sleep and instantly reveals it: "Seeing the outside snow." Wright's poetic calibre achieved perfection whenever he exhibited the contrast of black and white. This juxtaposition is emblematic of the color line of

Douglass or the veil of DuBois, which always remains there as a reminder of the racially stratified society and the discrimination they were compelled to endure for having black skin.

Snow imagery resonates with Wright's broader concerns regarding race, society, and the human condition. "Snow in the back of a cow" (107), "the horns of cow steeply slanting snow." (325), black cock in snow (523), snow spotted kitten (665), these visually captivating phrases often accentuate the demarcation of black and white. A quintessential line appears in haiku (166)

The snow on the bank/stains the river water black

Similar haiku emphasise the color line by juxtaposing snow and dark objects.

A big black umbrella

In the falling snow (373)

From the frozen black timbers/ Of a burnt down house (414)

Black poles are boasting

To the snowy field (702)

Under the dark hedges

Are patches of white (746)

A black rat creeps along

A path in the snow (790)

To intensify the contrast of black and white which served as an instrument for manifesting the veil or the color line, Wright delineated images like melting snow on the brown horseback,

(61) icy fog, white faced cow (344), snow-spotted kitten (665), black man sweeping the falling snow (609), enough snow to make a stunting black cock.

Snow imagery emerges as a recurrent pattern in Wright's haiku, only to accentuate the pain of alienation and social isolation. The white colour of the snow represents the white skin colour of white people, the colour which is much desired, even sometimes coveted by the black people, as the source of their misery is the black colour of their skin. Therefore, both white and black coloured objects are juxtaposed to manifest the metaphorical color line. The coldness and starkness of winter symbolise the despondency of loneliness and segregation, accompanied by the hardships, challenges, and impediments experienced by black people in a racially stratified society. This coldness also indicated the nonchalance and indifference displayed by the white people towards the black people. Snow imagery also resonates with the broader concerns Wright contemplated regarding race, society, and the human condition. By adroitly using snow imagery, Wright delved deep into the psychological realm of a black persona. Wright unveiled the mental repercussions of being racially discriminated against through the imagery. It can be considered a visual representation of the innermost thoughts of a black person who resides in a society insupportable for their development, with a fragmented personality.

Works Cited:

Aberjhani, West, Sandra L., *Harlem Renaissance, Encyclopaedia of the Harlem Renaissance Renaissance*, Checkmark Books, 2003, New York, USA, ISBN 0-8160-4540-2

Abrams, M.H. *A Glossary of Literary Terms*, Heinle and Heinle, Cornell University. USA, ISBN-0-15-505452-x, 1999

Snow and the Veil: A Critical Study of the Symbolism of Snow in Richard Wright's *Haiku*

Albert in C. Barnes, *Negro Art in America, in The New Negro: An Interpretation*, Ed, Locke, Alain, Albert and Charles Boni, New York, ISBN-9780384332805,1925

Cesaire, Aime, *Discourse on Colonialism: A Poetics of Anticolonialism*, trans. Kelly, Robin D.G. Monthly Review Press, New York, ISBN-13-978-1-58367-025-5,1972

Cuddon, J.A., *A Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory*, Wiley-Blackwell, USA, ISBN-978-1-4433-3327-5, 2013

DuBois, W.E.B. *The Soul of Black Folk*, Ed. Henry Louis Gates, Oxford University Press, New York, ISBN-978-0-19-531180-8,

Ed. Wright, Ellen and Michel Fabre, *Richard Wright Reader*, Da Capo Press. New York, ISBN-0-306-80774-3,1997

Fanon, Frantz, *Black Skin, White Masks*, trans. Markmann, Charles, Lam, Pluto Press, London, 1986 ISBN-0745300359pbk

Ed. Farebrother, Rachel, and Tygart, Miriam, *African American Literature in Transition 1920-1930*, Cambridge University Press, UK, ISBN-9781108834162,2022

Hall, Joshua M. *The Necessary Pain of Moral Imagination: Lonely Delegation in Richard Wright's Haiku and White Man, Listen* (Pg. 63–64)

Wright, Richard, *Haiku: This Other World*, Ed. Hakutani, Yoshinobu, and Tener, Robert L. Arcade Publishing, New York,1998, ISBN-978-1-61145-349-2

Wright, Richard, *White Man, Listen!* Harper Perennial, California, ISBN-0-06-092564-7,1995